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pp. 59–77 **Kremlin's Political Myths of 2022**

Mity polityczne Kremla roku 2022

Abstract

Keywords Russian-Ukrainian war, diabolisation of West, deification of Russia, political myths

We can understand Putin by analysing the myths in his speeches. The analysis draws upon the author's typology of myths: saviour *versus* Lucifer, "golden age" *versus* the "tribulation age," and conspiracy *versus* unity. Putin treats the US as absolute evil, Lucifer. Deified Russia will free the world from this evil. The West is conspiratorially controlled, but its population may "wake up," and will support Russia. It is imperative to implement the "golden age" of the world. Otherwise, there will be the "tribulation age" headed by the US. The above vision of the world bestows a feature of good and right and the impression of rationality to use any means and methods to destroy the enemy, which is the whole West allied with the US.

Streszczenie

Słowa kluczowe wojna Rosji z Ukrainą, diabolizacja Zachodu, deifikacja Rosji, mity polityczne

Zrozumieć Putina można w następstwie analizy mitów występujących w jego przemówieniach. Analiza ta odwołuje się do autorskiej typologii mitów: zbawca *versus* Lucyfer, „złoty wiek” *versus* „wiek ucisku” oraz konspiracja *versus* jedność. Putin traktuje Stany Zjednoczone Ameryki jak absolutne zło, Lucyfera. Deifikowana Rosja uwolni świat od tego zła. Zachód jest konspiracyjnie sterowany, ale możliwe jest jego „przebudzenie się”, a więc opowiedzenie się za Rosją. Konieczne jest nadejście „złotego wieku” w skali świata, inaczej czeka nas „wiek ucisku” przez Stany Zjednoczone. Powyższa wizja świata nadaje cechy dobroci, słuszności i wrażenia racjonalności polityce stosowania dowolnych środków i sposobów zniszczenia wroga, jakim jest cały Zachód sprzymierzony ze Stanami Zjednoczonymi.

Introduction

What myths organise the thinking of the Kremlin's ruling elite in Russia? This question acquires even greater importance the more risky decisions the Kremlin makes, and the more they affect Russia and its entire external environment. It, therefore, takes on a particularly dramatic dimension during the war with Ukraine and becomes exceptionally crucial with the repeated announcements of the possibility of using nuclear weapons in this conflict.

The decision of unprovoked aggression against Ukraine, launched on 24 February 2022, was highly irrational, and its results not only fell short of expectations but also contrary to them. There are many indications that the decisions to declare mobilisation and to annex incompletely occupied Ukrainian territories will produce similar results. However, a few weeks after they were made, it was already known that they significantly reduced the pool of scenarios that the Kremlin could consider. In such a case, it is necessary to analyse thinking not so much on a rational level but through the prism of political myths propagated by the Kremlin.

The highest Kremlin representative authorised to announce decisions and provide justifications for them is President of the Russian Federation (hereafter—the RF) Vladimir Putin, which is why his official speeches are so important. Each of them is prepared by his closest associates, and top officials from the decision-making elite provide the materials for many of them. Thus, these speeches reflect not only the point of view of Putin himself but also the thinking of Russia's ruling elite.

The article aims to determine what type of political myths represents the thinking of the highest member of the Kremlin elite ruling Russia in the first year of the war with Ukraine. The next task is to determine the level of intensity of specific manifestations of mythical thinking. The text consists of five parts: the first one presents the most important typologies of political myths and reports on Raoul Girardet's innovative attempt to modify the typology of myths significantly; the second deals with the methodology of the research; the third and fourth parts present analyses of Putin's political myths from February and September 2022, and the last part contains a summary.

Typologies of Political Myths

Political myths serve to justify the actions of dominant or aspiring political actors. In the first case, they are a tool for legitimisation, and in the second—for delegitimisation of ruling classes or elites. Their role increases significantly in crises, weakening social cohesiveness and widespread uncertainty.¹ Myths give their followers a sense of meaning, causality, and possession of rightness. An important role of all myths is to provide hope for the future and, in the case of legitimising myths, to justify the present situation. At the same time, myths offer patterns of desirable and undesirable behaviour.² Myths

¹ N. Sviličić, P. Maldini, "Political Myths and Totalitarianism. An Anthropological Analysis of Their Causal Interrelationship," *Collegium Antropologicum* 2014, Vol. 38, No. 2, pp. 725–738.

² M. Eliade, *Aspekty mitu*, transl. P. Mrówczyński, Warszawa: Wydawnictwo KR, 1998, p. 8.

are neither true nor false; thus, it is unimportant to what extent they differ from reality. Far more important is a picture of the world they create.

There are many typologies of political myths, so it is worth mentioning the most important ones. Adopting the time criterion makes it possible for us to distinguish historical, contemporary, and prospective myths. As regards the attitude to the dominant culture, myths can be vitalistic (acceptance of this culture), counter-cultural (its negation, exclusion), nativist (striving for the revival of the own decaying culture), and auto-negative (negation of one's own culture).³

In the 1980s, Raoul Girardet created the most common typology of political myths concerning non-democratic structures. He categorised myths into four groups: conspiracy, unity, saviour, and "golden age" myths. The myth of conspiracy is based on the existence of darkness, mysteriousness, and secrecy of a few, though most often powerful, groups or individuals who seek to destroy "our" concord, harmony, and unity. In this sense, it is opposed to the myth of unity. "We"—the common people, the oppressed nation, the poor people, society—must be united in order to survive and overcome any evil that the "Elders of Zion," the Freemasons, Soros' latent cohort, etc., want to inflict on us. The rallying of people denoted by "us," the mobilisation of their time, attention, and efforts is possible, and the more significant and threatening the myth of the enemy conspiracy is, the greater is this mobilisation.⁴ The saviour myth comes in several varieties: the hero, the ordinary man, the nation's leader or the firm ("iron") man among politicians.⁵ The saviour can lead a united people to a "golden age." The latter is a state in which prosperity, beauty and happiness will reign, thanks to the fact that there will be no more evil.⁶

Girardet's typology is an inspiring theoretical exploratory scheme. It is based on three primary criteria: the division of "us" and "them," the setting of goals, and their implementation by the leader (hierarchical structure). The first criterion corresponds to the myths of conspiracy and unity, that is, of negating and restoring harmony; the second—to the prospective myth of the "golden age," and the third—to the myth of the saviour.

In the case of the first criterion, it is possible to treat the myths of conspiracy and unity as two antinomic ideal types. Thus, there are darkness and disunity, conspiracy, and hostility on the one side, while on the other, there are brightness, harmony, friendship, and brotherhood. If we regard the myth of the "golden age" as an ideal type, it is possible to construct an antinomian ideal type—the myth of the age of oppression and persecution—the "tribulation age". The antinomy of the saviour myth as a perfect type is the myth of Lucifer cast down to hell. These three dyads of ideal antinomian types make it possible to create a theoretical tool to analyse political myths, especially in the case of non-democratic social structures. However, for this tool to become precise, it is

³ E. Nowicka, *Bunt i ucieczka*, Warszawa: Państwowe Wydawnictwo Naukowe, 1972, *passim*; R. Bäcker, *Nietradycyjna teoria polityki*, Toruń: Wydawnictwo Naukowe Uniwersytetu Mikołaja Kopernika w Toruniu, 2011, pp. 53–60.

⁴ R. Girardet, *Mythes et mythologies politiques*, Paris: Editions du Seuil, 1986.

⁵ R.G. Schwartzberg, *The Superstar Show of Government*, Bucharest: Scripta Publishing House, 1995, pp. 14–15.

⁶ M.S. Stoica, "Political Myths of the Populist Discourse," *Journal for the Study of Religions and Ideologies* 2017, Vol. 16, No. 46, pp. 63–76.

necessary to create detailed types that delineate the appropriate places on the continua between these antinomomic ideal types.

The myths: saviour and Lucifer were very well concretised by Joanna Rak. She distinguished a total of eight detailed types. Closest to the ideal saviour type, she located the deification (anthropolatric) myth, which regards a person or community as a deity. The next myth—the theophanic—treats some entity as ideal, although not possessing divine qualities. The myth of the divine *mesistos* depicts an intermediary between god and humans, having good intentions towards them and acting for their benefit. The myth of the *katechon*, in turn, is lower in terms of positive valorisation than that of the divine *mesistos*. It treats a chosen individual, group or organisation as holding back evil from its destructive influence on the world. The antinomian ideal type also consists of four specific types. Closest to the ideal type is the diabolic myth, characterised by the possession of all the essential features of absolute evil; it is the antinomy of divinity. Slightly further from the ideal type is the demonic myth, in which the entity is evil because of its characteristics. Another specific type is the diabolical *mesistos*, who is an intermediary between the forces of evil and humans—he has sinister intentions, and such are the results of his actions for the people to whom he provides a false service. The last type is the myth of the antichrist (antinomian to the *katechon*), attributing to man the powers of stimulating the action of evil, initiating and accelerating the destruction of reality.⁷

In the last two cases, creating the author's typology became necessary. The myth of conspiracy and, antinomian to it, the myth of unity mark the extreme points of a continuum stretching between the strength of the world of darkness and evil, and the world of unity, brightness, and goodness. The greater the reign of the world of evil, the smaller the good, and vice versa. The world of unity, goodness, and brightness is the most intense when “we” and all those who can be “us” encompass the entire globe. However, few exceptions, such as those who want to rule the world, may exist. Usually, in such a case, the Zionist conspiracy, alienated elites of certain countries, large corporations or the “golden billion” are mentioned.⁸ The next stage is a potential world of unity and clarity in many areas of the globe. Perfectly suited for this is the figure of the “dormant” people, whose “objective interests” oppose the world of evil. The third stage is the reign of the world of unity in an area that belongs to “us,” if only for geopolitical, historical or other reasons that justify imperial aspirations. The fourth stage is the potential for the existence of such a world of unity in areas belonging to us in the form of oppressed nations dreaming of joining their “true motherland.” The fifth stage is the undisputed reign of the world of good in our homeland, with few exceptions of extremists and troublemakers. The sixth

⁷ Cf. J. Rak, “The Typological Framework of Myths as a Tool for Studying Political Thought,” *World Political Science* 2018, Vol. 14, No. 2, p. 15; J. Rak, “Siatka typologiczna mitów jako narzędzie do badania myśli politycznej,” [in:] *Azjatyckie pogranicza kultury i polityki*, J. Marszałek-Kawa, K. Kakareko (eds), Toruń: Wydawnictwo Adam Marszałek, 2017, pp. 191–226. The names of the categories “diabolical” and “demonic” have been slightly modified.

⁸ Vide J. Diec, “Funkcje syndromu postradzieckiego w pozimnowojennym łądziej międzynarodowym,” [in:] *Rozpad ZSRR i jego konsekwencje dla Europy i świata*, Vol. 3: *Kontekst międzynarodowy*, idem (ed.), Kraków: Księgarnia Akademicka, 2011; S.S. Ryabova, P.A. Potapov, “The Concept of Sustainable Development as the Representation of Postmodernism,” *Vestnik MGSU* 2013, Vol. 8, No. 9, pp. 70–78. According to the theory of the “golden billion” only a small proportion of humanity can benefit from globalisation.

stage is the existence of a strong “fifth column,” lurking inside our besieged fortress for any weaknesses in the world of good. The seventh and final stage is the dominance of the world of evil on our territory in the form of, for example, Time of Troubles (*smuta*) or a victorious “colour revolution” inspired, directed, and paid for by hostile, external forces of the global conspiracy.

The myth of the “golden age” and its antinomian myth of the “tribulation age” mark the extremes of a continuum whose main criterion is independence from “outsiders,” that is, all those who conspire against “us.” Total subordination to “outsiders,” and their standing over all matters concerning “us” testify to the reign of the age of oppression. Liberation from “outsiders” begins when our leader (the leader of the nation) begins to pursue a policy different from the will and aspirations of “outsiders.” This process of liberation from “outsiders” ends at the moment of a particular rebellion—an open rejection of obedience to “outsiders” made by the leader. The third stage is building the power to oppose the “outsiders.” The fourth is to make the “outsiders” accept our equal status, that is, their acceptance of our position as utterly independent of them. The fifth is the struggle to obtain this status by eliminating “outsiders” from “our” territory or sphere of influence that does not belong to them. The sixth stage is to gain superiority over the “outsiders,” and the last—the seventh—is to isolate ourselves from the “outsiders” completely or to destroy them, which signifies the reign of a “golden age” in “our” territory or even the entire globe, i.e. universal happiness and prosperity.

The first dyad of myths of conspiracy and unity legitimises the expansionist struggle against the outside world up to its extreme, i.e. the destruction of the entire realm of evil. The second dyad of myths, i.e. the “golden age” on the one side and oppression on the other, legitimises isolationist tendencies, i.e. the pursuit of separation from the rest of the world. It can be difficult to distinguish one legitimising tendency from another, especially when defining one’s territory is ambiguous. It is especially true for empires in periods of instability, that is, mainly in the early or declining stages.

These three antinomic dyads of types of ideal political myths: saviour and Lucifer, conspiracy and unity, and “golden age” and the era of oppression (“tribulation age”) form a primary grid of theoretical categories. It is a convenient tool for examining all manifestations of political thought, especially those occurring in autocratic structures.

Methodological Assumptions

Russian political thinking under President Putin has already been analysed many times,⁹ so there is no need to revisit the origins of the political ideas of the Russian “Leader of

⁹ O. Nadszakula-Kaczmarczyk, “Negatywna tożsamość a rosyjskie myślenie polityczne,” *Studia Orientalne* 2020, No. 1(17), pp. 29–43; R. Bäcker, *Rosyjskie myślenie polityczne za czasów prezydenta Putina*, Toruń: Wydawnictwo Adam Marszałek, 2007; P. Rojek, *Przekleństwo imperium. Źródła rosyjskiego zachowania*, Kraków: Wydawnictwo M, 2014; M. Kragh, E. Andermo, L. Makashova, “Conspiracy Theories in Russian Security Thinking,” *Journal of Strategic Studies* 2022, Vol. 45, No. 3, pp. 334–368; J. Rak, R. Bäcker, “Theory behind Russian Quest for Totalitarianism. Analysis of Discursive Swing in Putin’s Speeches,” *Communist and Post-Communist Studies* 2020, Vol. 53, No. 1, pp. 13–26.

the Nation” in 2022. However, the significant transformation of the situation not only in Russia and Ukraine but also in the world after February 2022 made it necessary to take up the topic anew. The basis of the study are the Russian president’s most important public speeches from the beginning of the aggression against Ukraine to the annexation into the RF of four Ukrainian regions incompletely controlled by the aggressor’s troops, i.e. in the period from the second half of February to the end of September 2022.

The purpose of the study will be achieved by solving the following research problem: How can Putin’s official statements be situated on the continuum between the antinomic ideal types of political myths of a) saviour and Lucifer, b) conspiracy and unity, c) the “golden age” and “tribulation age”? This, in turn, can be resolved by answering the following questions: Where on the continuum, with regard to the pejorative types of ideal political myths (Lucifer, conspiracy and the age of oppression), is the vision of the West situated? The same question should also be asked about the vision of Ukraine. The last question concerns the place of Russia’s vision on the continuum on the side of the meliorative types of ideal political myths (saviour, unity, and “golden age”).

In this case, it will be necessary to apply the method of critical text analysis in qualitative terms. The analysis unit will be the individual wordings contained in Putin’s speeches. Extracting them and then assigning them to the corresponding detailed types on the continua between the antinomic ideal types of political myths will make it possible to create a map of the epiphenomena of political myths. Making this map will lead to the answer to the specific questions and, consequently, to the solution to the main problem.

The fundamental corpus of sources for the considerations will be Putin’s most important public speeches from the recognition of the so-called Donetsk People’s Republic and Luhansk People’s Republic, that is, the decision to launch an aggression against Ukraine, to the signing of the decree on mobilisation in Russia and the formal annexation of Ukrainian territories only partially controlled by the Russian army. The most important speeches published on the RF president’s official website include four speeches: two from February and two from September.

The first was delivered on 21 February and concerned the recognition of the independence of the so-called Donetsk People’s Republic and the Luhansk People’s Republic. The second February speech was broadcast in the early morning of 24 February and was a proclamation to soldiers. The two documents should be viewed together not only because of their temporal proximity but also because of their thematic convergence and the repeated references made in the second speech to the earlier one.

The structure of Putin’s understanding of the world becomes clearer after presenting the ratio of the number of words in his speeches devoted to particular issues. The first speech mentioned above was overwhelmingly devoted to the history and an assessment of Ukraine’s internal situation—it was 4151 words out of 6165, or just over two-thirds of the speech’s time (67.3 per cent to be exact). In turn, 1527 words (24.8 per cent of the total) Putin devoted to presenting his views on the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (hereafter—NATO). He discussed the situation in Donbas, using only 344 words (5.6 per cent of the total). The second speech (of 24 February) had different proportions: 1149 + 193 words (out of 3041, or 44.1 per cent) dealt with NATO policy, including the United States in particular, while 774 words (or 25.5 per cent) dealt with Russia,

including the 1941–1945 war with Germany and the need to defend Russia against its enemies; 251 words (8.3 per cent) dealt with the situation in Ukraine; and 633 words (20.8 per cent) dealt with the goals and principles of the so-called special military operation. A significant portion of both speeches (24.8 per cent and 44 per cent, respectively) was devoted to presenting views on the United States and NATO. The characterisation of Ukraine had incomparable shares (67.3 per cent and 8.3 per cent). In contrast, the situation in the Donbas, even though it was the formal subject of the first speech and the cause of the so-called military special operation described in the second, occupied only 5.6 per cent of the former and an insignificant portion of the latter. Putin treated the Donbas marginally in both speeches, and the most crucial issue for him appeared to be the subordination of Ukraine to the West's strategic plans.

In September 2022, the president of the Russian Federation delivered two important speeches. The first was broadcast live on television on 21 September and was addressed to the Russian people for the first time during the war. Putin gave the second speech on 30 September on the occasion of the signing of agreements on the incorporation of occupied Ukrainian lands into the territory of Russia. In the first speech, out of 1,552 words, he devoted 405 (26.1 per cent) to the West, as many as 455 (29.3 per cent) to the “neo-Nazi” regime in Ukraine, and the remainder dealt with the details of the so-called partial mobilisation announced in that address. The 30 September speech to the participants in the annexation celebration (and thus the ruling elite) was more than twice as long, at 3884 words. The dominant part of this speech (a total of 2447 words, or 63 per cent) was a description of the evil West. Putin devoted 122 words, or 3.1 per cent, to presenting the crimes committed by the “neo-Nazi” Ukrainian regime. The rest of the speech was dedicated to Russia's mission and the creation of historical and moral justifications for annexing the lands of the so-called Novorossiia.¹⁰

All four speeches paint a picture of Putin's mythical thinking. This thinking concerns three fundamental issues: understanding the West, treating Ukraine, and comprehending Russia.

The Mythicism of Justifications for Aggression against Ukraine

The decision to send Russian troops to conquer Ukraine was utterly irrational.¹¹ Instead of an instant and triumphant victory, the Russian army had to withdraw entirely from the northern front and, for many months in 2022, fought less and less victorious battles on the southern and eastern fronts. So how did Putin view the West, Ukraine and Russia itself at the time of his decision to launch the aggression?

¹⁰ Novorossiia, as Putin understands it, includes an area stretching north from the Crimea to the borders of Moldova, *vide* A. Шарый, “Новороссия... Что за земля?” [A. Sharyy, “Novorossiia... Chto za zemlya?”], *Svoboda*, 26 April 2014, <<https://www.svoboda.org/a/25363270.html>> (accessed on 14.01.2023).

¹¹ R. Bäcker, J. Rak, “Why did Putin Go Too Far? The Rationality of Vladimir Putin's Decision to Begin a War with Ukraine,” *Society Register* 2022, Vol. 6, No. 3, pp. 57–72.

The US-led NATO is seen as an aggressive military alliance seeking, by all means, to subjugate more and more territories formerly belonging to the Soviet sphere of influence. According to Putin, NATO never intended to treat Russia as a possible ally or an actual partner. The sole and most important objective of the United States and the entire subordinate machine was to weaken and then destroy Russia as much as possible. The United States is treated as an enemy that uses all possible despicable means to achieve its goals: deceitful lies, armaments, the construction of military bases and installations on territories that do not belong to it and, what is more, were those for which Russian soldiers shed blood as far back as the 18th century. These are only some of the accusations made against the West. The image of an aggressive United States using NATO as an instrument is reinforced by citing examples of military interventions in the former Yugoslavia, Libya, Syria, and Iraq. Putin does not mention the example of Afghanistan in his speech on the morning of 24 February.¹² In consequence, according to Putin, practically everywhere the West comes to establish its order, there are bloody, non-healing wounds, abscesses of international terrorism and extremism.¹³ In this sense, NATO is a worldwide instrument of universal evil.

The United States is described as a state wishing to be a hegemon and, to this end, using only immoral means: cynical lies and deceit, attempts at pressure and blackmail, which is related to the US leaders' conviction of its uniqueness, sinlessness and, therefore, the possibility of doing whatever they want. What does not align with the will of the hegemon, the people in power, is treated as archaic, obsolete and unnecessary. Conversely: everything that is convenient for them is regarded as the essential and revealed truth (*istina*¹⁴) in the last instance and is implemented, according to Putin, at all costs, i.e. brutally and by all means. The conclusion of the Russian "Leader of the Nation" is thus simple: the United States is an empire of evil.¹⁵ The repetition of this Ronald Reagan's phrase concerning the USSR was meant to be a kind of culmination of the description of the worst imperial characteristics embodied by the United States.¹⁶

The picture of an evil empire would be incomplete without juxtaposing traditional values and pseudo-values. According to Kremlin propaganda, American pseudo-values decompose the nation from within, directly leading it to degradation and degeneration as being against the very nature of man.¹⁷ Such formulations are standard among the Russian power elite and gain expression, for example, in the law on the defence

¹² "Обращение Президента Российской Федерации" ["Obrashcheniye Prezidenta Rossiyskoy Federatsii"], 24 February 2022, 06:00 am, <kremlin.ru/events/president/news/67851> (accessed on 20.10.2022).

¹³ *Ibidem*.

¹⁴ More on the meaning of the term *istina* in Russian strategic culture *vide* I. Wiltenburg, "The Importance of Understanding Russian Strategic Culture," *Atlantisch Perspectief* 2020, Vol. 44, No. 1, pp. 7–12.

¹⁵ "Обращение Президента Российской Федерации"..., 24 February 2022.

¹⁶ G.Th. Goodnight, "Ronald Reagan's Re-Formulation of the Rhetoric of War. Analysis of the 'Zero Option,' 'Evil Empire,' and 'Star Wars' Addresses," *Quarterly Journal of Speech* 1986, Vol. 72, No. 4, pp. 390–414; R.C. Rowland, J.M. Jones, "Reagan's Strategy for the Cold War and the Evil Empire Address," *Rhetoric & Public Affairs* 2016, Vol. 19, No. 3, pp. 427–463.

¹⁷ "Обращение Президента Российской Федерации"..., 24 February 2022.

of traditional values¹⁸ allowing the repression of LGBT communities. However, in this morning's call for war with Ukraine, the juxtaposition of good and evil in sexual behaviour is highly generalising and antinomian. In this dimension, the war against Ukraine becomes not only the conquest of territory but also a metaphysical struggle against an amoral beast seeking the destruction of fundamental human values.

Putin does not see the multi-subject nature of NATO, and he does not see the sovereign will of the nations and states seeking membership in this military alliance. For him, NATO is a uniform machine led by a single-command centre that is aggressive and full of ill will towards Russia. It is a vision of a centrally controlled juggernaut of evil and destruction. In this mindset, US-led NATO can be seen as the most extreme stage of the Lucifer myth and, therefore, the total personification of evil. The image of the United States making all the running in NATO is close to the ideal type of conspiracy myth. These politicians want to rule the world, and, above all, desire to control Russia. However, this is not the most extreme level of evil, conspiracy, and darkness because there is a good Russia. In the case of the dyad of two myths—the “golden age” and the antinomic age of oppression—it is possible to situate Putin's understanding of the situation between the third and fourth stages. Russia is building the power to counter the “hostile” NATO, and the decision to launch a “special military operation” is nothing more than the realised desire to achieve an equal position with these “outsiders.”

In both of Putin's speeches, two myths about Ukraine are evident. The first is a historical myth—Ukraine, according to Putin, came into being thanks to Lenin's decisions, with successive general secretaries of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union freely shaping its territorial borders. Ukraine itself has no tradition of its actual statehood. In other words: Ukraine's state structure is artificial and solely the result of decisions made in the last hundred years in the Kremlin. In Putin's view, Ukraine is an inseparable part of Russian history, culture, and shared spiritual space. Ukrainians are relatives, colleagues, co-workers, and friends of Russians, and in many cases, people related to Russians by family ties.¹⁹ Ukraine is considered an inseparable part of Russia on all possible levels—historical, cultural, spiritual (including not only Orthodoxy), and the “proper” political structure. It is a repetition of the theses presented in an article signed by Putin and published on 12 July 2021, under the title “On the Historical Unity of the Russian and Ukrainian Peoples.”²⁰ According to Putin, Ukrainians, Belarusians, and Russians have formed a “triune Russian nation” for centuries; thus, Ukraine cannot be regarded as an entity independent of the Kremlin.

¹⁸ “Внесены законопроекты в защиту традиционных ценностей” [“Vneseny zakonoprojekty v zashchitu traditsionnykh tsennostey”], 20 October 2022, <<http://duma.gov.ru/news/55560/>> (accessed on 13.01.2023).

¹⁹ “Обращение Президента Российской Федерации” [“Obrashcheniye Prezidenta Rossiyskoy Federatsii”], 21 February 2022, <<http://kremlin.ru/events/president/news/67828>> (accessed on 13.01.2023).

²⁰ В. Путин, “Об историческом единстве русских и украинцев” [V. Putin “Ob istoricheskom yedinstve russkikh i ukrainitsev”], 12 July 2021, <<http://www.kremlin.ru/events/president/news/66181>> (accessed on 13.01.2023); *vide etiam* T. Rogan, “Decoding Putin's Phreat to Ukraine,” <<https://www.washingtonexaminer.com/opinion/decoding-putins-threat-to-ukraine>>, 13 July 2021 (accessed on 13.01.2023).

The historical myth about Ukraine is compatible with its contemporary myth. The latter is Ukraine through Putin's eyes since 2014, when Ukraine began to be ruled by not pro-Russian political teams. Maydan, in this sense, was the source of all the evils currently being experienced by Ukraine; its participants ("radicals") staged the state coup (forcing President Viktor Yanukovich to flee), and with the help of foreign centres. A wave of pogroms and violence, humiliation and murder with impunity accompanied their seizure of power. This is what led Ukraine to a civil war. In Putin's understanding, this last term served to describe the action of seizing power in Donetsk, Luhansk, and Crimea by Russian volunteers and soldiers without any identifying marks.²¹ In this way of understanding, all actions directed against the pro-Russian president (and therefore Russia itself) are evil, while good are all those carried out in the interests of and at the behest of the Kremlin.

In Putin's view, Ukrainian nationalists have brought Ukraine to the status not so much of an economic and political protectorate as, in fact, to the level of a colony with a puppet regime. Elsewhere in his speech, Putin explicitly spoke of leading Ukraine to a loss of sovereignty. The argument for this statement was the appearance of foreign advisors, the activities of NGOs, and the existence of many other institutions. The latter included, above all, NATO. According to Putin, the holding of joint military exercises has led to the Ukrainian army and even individual military units and their subdivisions being able to be directly commanded by the NATO centre. According to Putin, the modernisation of airports and the construction by the Americans of a control centre for naval operations at Ochakiv are nothing more than the preparation of Ukraine's military infrastructure for the rapid reception of NATO military troops.²²

This way of thinking is characteristic of a black-and-white vision of the world. If Ukraine is not linked to Russia, then it is subordinated to the West, which is hostile to Russia; there is no other option. There is "us" on the one side, and our enemies are on the other. Anyone who is not with us, or worse, cooperates with the enemies, is not another enemy but becomes a tool of the enemy. In this mindset, it is impossible to nuance the picture of reality. If Russia is powerful, then its enemy must also be mighty. Others can be either our potential or actual allies or helpless instruments used by hostile forces.

Ukraine, in this sense, is controlled by treacherous elites selling out their entire country to an enemy that wants to destroy the whole "russkiy mir"²³—the Russian world made up of ethnic Russians, Belarusians, and Ukrainians. The fight against the "nationalist and neo-Nazi" elites destroying this Russian world is, therefore, not only the responsibility

²¹ I. Katchanovski, "The Separatist War in Donbas. a Violent Break-Up of Ukraine?," *European Politics and Society* 2016, Vol. 17, No. 4, pp. 473–489; T. Bukkvoll, "Why Putin Went to War. Ideology, Interests and Decision Making in the Russian Use of Force in Crimea and Donbas," *Contemporary Politics* 2016, Vol. 22, No. 3, pp. 267–282.

²² "Обращение Президента Российской Федерации"... , 21 February 2022.

²³ Vide Z. Gasimov, "Idee und Institution. 'Russkij mir' zwischen kultureller Mission und Geopolitik," *Osteuropa* 2012, Vol. 62, No. 5, pp. 69–80; O. Zaborko, "Russkij Mir und Novorossija. Theologische und nationalistische Konzepte russischer (Außen-) Politik," [in:] *Kampf um die Ukraine. Ringen um Selbstbestimmung und geopolitische Interessen*, H.G. Justenhoven (ed.), Baden-Baden: Nomos–Aschendorff Verlag, 2018, pp. 63–78; M. Delong, "'Ruski mir' jako narzędzie rosyjskiej ekspansji geopolitycznej na terytorium Ukrainy," *Przegląd Geopolityczny* 2020, Vol. 33, pp. 50–64.

of Russia but also of ethnic “conscious” Ukrainians. The destruction of such elites is in line with the natural and true interests not only of the triune Russian world, but also of the Ukrainian people themselves. For it is in the latter’s interests to cooperate harmoniously with the other nations of the Russian world.

In the morning speech of 24 February 2022, we read that Russia does not want to violate the interests of Ukraine and the Ukrainian people. These interests are related to Russia’s defence against those who have taken Ukraine hostage and are trying to use it against “our” country and its people.²⁴ In this sense, Ukrainian interests are treated as identical (or, more accurately, harmoniously intertwined) with Russian interests. Treacherous elites and a dormant nation, yearning in its core for liberation from the former, are one of the semantic figures typical of totalitarian political gnosis.²⁵ At the same time, it is part of the myth of the saviour striving to make all those who need it happy, although they do not necessarily realise it. However, due to the lack of more precise identifications of Russia in these two analysed speeches, it is impossible to determine to which stage of the saviour myth it can be assigned.

The aggression against Ukraine was utterly irrational in logical terms; however, it becomes understandable when analysing the myths prevailing in the Kremlin elite. The United States with the US-led NATO and broadly defined West fulfil all the criteria of a diabolical myth—the embodiment of absolute evil. Ukraine’s ruling elite is a diabolical *mesistos* with no autonomous meaning. By its very nature, Ukraine is an inseparable part of the Russian world, and any attempt to absorb it into the Western world goes against Ukraine’s natural destiny. In such a situation, Russia’s duty is to restore the natural world order. This is an even more important task since Russia represents goodness, unity and clarity, while the West represents evil, darkness and conspiratorial scheming.

The Mythicism of Putin’s Thinking During the Annexation of the Occupied Territories and the Mobilisation

The planned mobilisation of 300,000 men and its possible supplementation with another 100,000 soldiers who were completing their basic military service and encouraged to sign contracts will not change the situation of the Russian army. It will continue to be inferior to the Ukrainian army in terms of training, armament, command skills, and level of motivation to fight. In such a situation, the general outcome of the fight is pretty easy to predict. Incorporating the occupied territories into the RF did not result in a cease-fire by the Ukrainian army or a declaration by Kyiv of a willingness to hold peace talks

²⁴ “Обращение Президента Российской Федерации”..., 24 February 2022.

²⁵ For more *vide* E. Voegelin, *The New Science of Politics. An Introduction*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1952 (edited in Polish as: *Nowa nauka polityki*, transl. P. Śpiewak, Warszawa: Fundacja Aletheia, 1992); A. Besançon, *Les origines intellectuelles du léninisme*, Paris: Calmann-Lévy, 1977; R. Bäcker, *Nietradycyjna teoria polityki*, Toruń: Wydawnictwo Naukowe Uniwersytetu Mikołaja Kopernika w Toruniu, 2011, pp. 179–198; J. Rak, “How to Measure Political Gnosis? Empirical Evidence from Putin’s Russia,” *Przegląd Polityczny* 2014, No. 4, pp. 159–171.

involving the recognition of the *status quo*. The result was only an increase in the stakes of this war. The Kremlin elite artificially moved the military operation into Russian territory and actually entered Russian homes, taking away several hundred thousand men by force. Could it be that Putin wants the “special military operation” to become a second Great Patriotic War?²⁶ This is a rhetorical question if only because Putin repeatedly compared the current situation with the period before the Nazi aggression against the Soviet Union in 1941.

Comparing the sizes of the different parts of the two speeches presented above reveals that Ukraine is not treated as the most important by Putin and his entourage. Far more important for the Kremlin elite is the attitude of the West and thus finding reasons for the apparent anti-Russian stance during this war. It is worth analysing, in this case, what the image of the West is in both of these speeches.

The West is personified as part of the ruling elite, with the United States at its centre. It is the latter that wants to be the hegemon of the whole world. This aspiration is pursued on all possible levels. Putin briefly described the ambition to subjugate the world in the economic sphere (“they want to loot us”²⁷). He devoted much more space to gender issues, clearly treating the “rainbow perspective” as impossible in Russia.²⁸ This traditionalist stance can be qualified as counter-cultural.

However, the most significant part of the description of the West was devoted to the United States’ quest for hegemony in the political and military fields. The ruling circles of this superpower seek to subjugate the entire world by continuing a policy of aggressive military colonialism. The speech on the occasion of the annexation of four Ukrainian regions included mention of the Opium Wars, the carpet bombing of German cities, and the atomic raids on Hiroshima and Nagasaki. According to Putin, the US has occupied Japan, Korea, and Germany so far, cynically calling these countries allies. Consequently, he calls the ruling circles of Western countries traitors to their own people because they are subservient to the United States and not to the true interests of their own people.²⁹ In this sense, the United States is treated as an eternal and all-embracing (including its closest allies) empire of absolute evil.

The US-led West, in this understanding, contributes to all kinds of misery. Murder, looting, and the destruction of everything are, according to Putin, the most severe results of the United States’ quest for hegemony. To conceal this, the West practices aggressive propaganda and lies like Goebbels.³⁰ According to the above understanding, evil is universal and all-embracing in the public sphere.

²⁶ The first was the war waged against the Nazi troops between 1941 and 1945. *Vide* D. Moskwa, “*Matka Ojczyzna wzywa!*” *Wielka wojna ojczyźniana w edukacji i polityce historycznej putinowskiej Rosji*, Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Instytutu Studiów Politycznych PAN, 2020.

²⁷ “Подписание договоров о принятии ДНР, ЛНР” Запорожской и Херсонской областей в состав России” [“Podpisanie dogovorov o prinyatii DNR, LNR, Zaporozhskoy i Khersonskoy oblastey v sostav Rossii”], 30 September 2022, <<http://kremlin.ru/events/president/news/69465>> (accessed on 14.01.2023).

²⁸ *Ibidem*.

²⁹ *Ibidem*.

³⁰ *Ibidem*.

The conclusion Putin draws is as follows: The West has an extreme disregard for the moral rights of billions of people, a vast part of humanity, especially law and justice and the right to decide freely about one's future. At the moment, Putin says, the West completely negates moral values, religion, and the family. Thus, the West also encroaches into the private sphere and destroys all good there.

Moreover, the West is an enemy not only of humanity but also of Russia. The former aims to weaken, divide, and ultimately destroy Russia. The aim is to deprive it of its political, economic, and cultural sovereignty and to plunder its lands thoroughly.³¹ The West has always dreamed of fragmenting Russia, of condemning its people to misery and extinction.³² And as proof of these words, Putin points to: the 17th-century Time of Troubles, 1917 and the 1990s, i.e. periods of the weakness of the Russian state, during which the West tried to subjugate it. A Russia, thus understood, by succumbing to the evil West in anything, shows its weakness. Therefore, the only way for it to survive is to oppose this evil personified by the West in every possible way.

It is the nature of the West to cause worldwide wars and crises just for its own personal bloody gain.³³ The West is then identified with the beast of war, treating it as wholly opposed to the true interests of humanity, anti-moral, anti-family, and forcing others and itself to do only evil are the defining characteristics of the extreme stage in the typology of the Lucifer myth. The myth of the West in Putin's September 2022 speeches is diabolical to the highest degree because the West, as presented in them, is the devil incarnate, the demiurge of evil, even Lucifer.

Ukraine, on the other hand, is treated by the Russian president as an object of hegemonic influence by the United States, seeking to subjugate the entire world. The phrase "the Kyiv authorities and their actual hosts in the West"³⁴ quite accurately reflects the Russian leader's understanding of the Ukrainian state. In fact, it was the West that turned the people of Ukraine into cannon fodder and pushed them towards war with Russia, stirring up criminal Russophobia in the process. At the same time, intimidation, terror, and violence were used to prevent Ukrainians from striving to realise their "essentially true" need to unite with Russia.³⁵ According to the President of the RF, the people living in Ukraine are, in fact, brothers and sisters of the Russians, an indigenous part of one nation artificially divided by the catastrophic break-up of the Soviet Union.³⁶ The annexation of the occupied areas of Ukraine then becomes nothing less than the restoration of historical unity.

Putin treats Ukraine's political elites at the level of diabolical *mesistos*. On the other hand, the people of Ukraine are understood as an arbitrarily shaped biomass with the precise conviction that their destiny is to find themselves back in Greater Russia.

³¹ "Обращение Президента Российской Федерации" ["Obrashcheniye prezidenta Rossiyskoy Federatsii"], 21 September 2022 <<http://kremlin.ru/events/president/news/69390>> (accessed on 14.01.2023).

³² "Подписание договоров о принятии ДНР, ЛНР" ...

³³ *Ibidem*.

³⁴ *Ibidem*.

³⁵ "Обращение Президента Российской Федерации" ..., 21 September 2022.

³⁶ "Подписание договоров о принятии ДНР, ЛНР" ...

Both of Putin's September 2022 speeches contain precise formulations of Russia's tasks. "A special military operation" thus becomes a necessary, pre-emptive move to avoid the inevitable attack by Ukrainian neo-Nazis upon the Donbas. This operation aims to liberate (and in another place, we read: "cleanse") the Donbas from neo-Nazis.³⁷ Putin says this in the course of annexing, among other things, the Kherson Oblast, which is north of Crimea and is not part of Donbas.

However, Russia's mission, according to Putin, is much more serious. In the conclusion of his speech on 21 September, he said that it is enshrined in Russian tradition, in the destiny of the Russian nation, to stop all those who want to rule the world, who threaten to dismember and enslave the homeland. This mission of Russia will be fulfilled now and in the future.³⁸ This conviction thus constitutes a clear and sharp contrast between the good represented by Russia and the evil identified with the West. Nine days later, this wording was made more specific. Putin said that the battlefield to which Russia had been summoned by history and fate—was the battlefield for the nation, for great historical Russia and for future generations. Therefore, all Russians must defend their children, grandchildren, and great-grandchildren from enslavement, from strange experiments leading to the mutilation of their consciousness and soul. According to Putin, what is being fought today is to ensure that it never occurs to anyone, ever, that Russia can be erased from the pages of history.³⁹ In this understanding, the war against Ukraine becomes a war for the survival of Russia itself, fundamental to its existence.

This apparently defensive concept ceases to be so when it turns out that the homeland is, in Putin's understanding, identical to a great imperial Russia. Its embodiment in the past was the "great and powerful" Soviet Union. Nowadays, Putin is striving to rebuild such a Russia. He wants it to be an essential part of a multipolar world. According to Putin, billions of people see in the existence of multiple independent powers in the world the possibility of stabilising their sovereignty, the right to enjoy genuine freedom, and the chance for independent, creative and original development, for harmony.⁴⁰ This is the dream not only of Russia having its own permanent spheres of influence but of all the other powers guaranteeing their inviolability. The cutting off of the "empire of evil" from Russia's spheres of influence does not, however, mean the end of the war for the universal reign of good throughout the world. The struggle between good and evil is, after all, permanent.

In Putin's understanding, Russia is not only a geographical space but also a community of values such as justice, sovereignty, freedom, and creativity—which improve the world and create harmony.⁴¹ According to Putin, these values must grow out of mercy, compassion, and humanity;⁴² Russia is the bearer of the most important ethical values and is identical to the moral ideal.

³⁷ "Обращение Президента Российской Федерации"..., 21 September 2022.

³⁸ *Ibidem*.

³⁹ "Подписание договоров о принятии ДНР, ЛНР"...

⁴⁰ *Ibidem*.

⁴¹ This is how the word *созидание* (*sozidanie*) can be translated.

⁴² "Подписание договоров о принятии ДНР, ЛНР"...

The final phrase of Putin's 30 September speech was as follows: "За нами–правда, за нами–Россия!"⁴³ ("With us–truth, with us–Russia!"). The conviction of having true knowledge of the world's future history is a typical feature of gnosis. In this understanding, Russia's destiny is not only to defend its historical (and therefore post-Soviet) territory but also to create a new world order. The fulfilment of this mission is only possible on the condition of a victorious struggle against the evil prevailing in the West.

This notion of Russia includes the most important essential features of the deification myth: it appears as a creation close to the ideal of a divine saviour. However, the act of salvation concerns not only Russia's own territory (defined by the borders of the Soviet empire) but also the entire world. In this sense, Russia is, therefore, the collective divine saviour of the world.

If we consider Putin's words from the perspective of the myth of the "golden age" on the one side and of the "oppression age" on the other, then Russia is clearly on the side of the former as its struggles to eliminate the "outsiders" from its historical lands. Once this is accomplished, an age of universal happiness and prosperity will reign in Russia, according to its leader, provided, of course, that the forces of evil throughout the world are overcome. Russia is undoubtedly in a world of unity and clarity. Already at the beginning of the 21st century, it has extricated itself from the reign of the forces of darkness and conspiracy that exploited the time of weakness of the Russian state in the 1990s. In 2022, Putin no longer mentions the "fifth column" he spoke of in 2014;⁴⁴ he treats Russia as having been cleansed of "conspiracy" forces. It is, therefore, necessary to "expurgate" the territories belonging to Russia from these forces and, at the same time, to "wake up" all those still dormant nations whose objective interest lies in liberating themselves from the rule of these "conspiracy" forces.

Conclusions

The four speeches by Putin analysed in the text were primarily devoted to the image of the West, Ukraine, and Russia itself. The quantitative analysis shows that the proportions of the volume of these topics were pretty similar. Out of 14642 words in all speeches, as many as 5721 (39 per cent) were about the West. To talk about Ukraine, Putin used 4979 words (34 per cent). This slight disproportion between the volumes of the individual issues indicates that the 'special military operation' is being treated as a stage in the global war against the West.

A qualitative analysis leads to similar conclusions. For the Kremlin's decision-making elite, the main enemy is the US-led West, not Ukraine. The Kremlin's ultimate goal is neither the 'cleansing' of the Donbas of neo-Nazis nor even the subjugation of the whole of Ukraine. These are only partial goals. Russia's most important goal, its mission and vocation, is to deprive the United States of its hegemony and ultimately to annihilate the West.

⁴³ *Ibidem*.

⁴⁴ R. Bäcker, J. Rak, "Epigonic Totalitarianism in Russia," *Politeja* 2019, Vol. 16, No. 5(62), pp. 7–19.

The decisions of military aggression against Ukraine, followed by partial mobilisation and annexation of occupied Ukrainian areas to Russia, were logically irrational. They produced no tangible results, compounded the costs and strengthened the resolve of the attacked and their allies to fight. Instead, these decisions become understandable if we consider them consequences of a mythical way of thinking.

This mythical mindset runs as follows: fighting evil is necessary and desirable. If the evil is the United States and the Western states that support it, then ‘we’ must fight them. The most crucial sub-goal in such a case is eliminating evil from ‘our,’ i.e. historically due, territory. This is a duty that must be pursued, whatever the cost. And this is only one stage in the fight against an evil far more powerful and threatening by its very existence, the very existence of Russia, its wholeness, cultural, civilisational and national-imperial identity. This battle is the most important and decisive one not only for the fate of Russia but also for the whole world. The absolute evil is the United States, and the diabolical *mesistos* are the ruling elites in all countries subordinate to it, not only in the wider West but also in Ukraine.

This way of thinking was already emerging before the Russian attack of February 2022. A significant part of Putin’s annual speeches at the joint sessions of the two chambers of the Russian quasi-parliament was devoted to descriptions of Russia’s vast superiority over the United States in the area of strategic nuclear weapons delivery. On 18 October 2018, at a meeting of the Valdai Club, Putin said: “We will go to paradise, and they will just perish.”⁴⁵ However, before the aggression against Ukraine, statements of the latter type were not frequent and were attempted to be marginalised quite efficiently. By contrast, numerous threats to use nuclear weapons have appeared systematically since the start of Russian aggression.

This makes it all the more worthwhile to compare Putin’s speeches from February and September 2022. The attitude towards Ukraine remains precisely the same, although it is evident in September that he limits himself to only one term (neo-Nazis). For Putin, both in February and September, Ukraine is effectively a state run by the West, especially the United States, and the Ukrainian people, according to him, who dream of reunification with their historic homeland, are subjected to numerous repressions. Ukraine’s ruling elites are constantly treated in terms of diabolical *mesistos*. A comprador and anti-national elite opposing the people’s essentially genuine aspirations is a fairly typical pattern of thinking to justify military aggression not only in modern Russia but also formerly in the USSR.

In the analysed speeches, Putin treats the United States and the subordinated West as the embodiment of absolute evil, identical to Lucifer. Only through the redemptive role of a deified Russia can the world be freed from this evil—multiform and seeking to control the world as a whole. Over time, the vision of the evil West and the world of absolute evil against which Russia fights become more thoroughly and more internalised in these speeches and become close to the ideal type of the myth of the divine saviour.

⁴⁵ “Путина спросили о перспективе россиян попасть в рай” [“Putina sprosili o perspektive rossiyan popast’ v ray”], 3 October 2019, <<https://dumatv.ru/news/putin-otvetil-pro-ray>> (accessed on 14.01.2023).

The myth of conspiracy and darkness in these speeches is attributed to the West, albeit with significant limitations, since the Russian leader sees an opportunity for the Western population to “wake up” and speak out against the absolute evil identified with the United States. All that is needed, therefore, is for the people to be made aware of their real interests and needs so that the era of evil not only in Ukraine but also in the West as a whole can come to an end. In Putin’s terms, therefore, Russia is waging war against the evils of the whole world, not just in Ukraine.

The fight against evil appeared in such a notion already in a speech in Munich in 2007, when Putin openly and harshly criticised the policies of the West, especially of the United States. This was an open denunciation of obedience to “outsiders” made by the “leader of the nation,” while Russia was working intensively on modernising its strategic military, including developing state-of-the-art nuclear weapon delivery means. Putin’s speeches before the Federal Assembly in the years leading up to the aggression against Ukraine primarily provided a description of these successes and served to gain acceptance by “outsiders” of Russia’s equal status and thus recognition of at least its role as a power with a vital sphere of influence. The failure of the West to accept the establishment of a “golden age” in the post-Soviet area resulted in Putin’s decision to forcibly eliminate “outsiders” from this territory that did not belong to them because it had belonged to great Russia for centuries. This protracted struggle against the forces of evil has led Putin to believe that it is necessary to reign in a “golden age,” not only in Russia’s territory but also in the whole world. Otherwise, the age of oppression will constantly threaten Russia and the world.

The above analysis of the positioning of Putin’s thinking at the intersection of the three antinomic dyads of myths allows the following conclusion to be drawn: the Kremlin’s vision of the world both justifies and imparts the quality of goodness, makes it right and rational to use all means and ways to destroy the enemy, including the use of weapons of mass destruction. This most important enemy is not only Ukraine but the entire West, led by the United States.

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